

INFORMED CONSENT

Title:

Energy drinks consumption and sleeping quality of students' universities of the Chiclayo province, Peru.

Purpose of the study:

Dear university student, we cordially invite you to participate in the research study entitled "Energy drink consumption and sleep quality among university students in Chiclayo, 2025." This study is being conducted by a group of researchers from César Vallejo University.

Procedures:

If you agree to participate, we need to inform you of the following:

- The questionnaire is online. You must read the questions carefully and select the option that best fits your situation.
- The estimated time to complete this questionnaire is approximately 15 minutes.

Risks:

Participating in this questionnaire does not involve any physical or psychological risk, nor will there be any legal or administrative repercussions if you decide to refuse to participate or not complete the questionnaire. We emphasize that this procedure is for academic and research purposes only.

Benefits:

If you decide to participate in this study, you will gain knowledge about the influence of energy drinks on sleep quality among the university population in Chiclayo city. This knowledge will form a basis that will contribute to future research that may provide solutions to this problem.

Costs and Incentives:

By participating in this study, you should be aware that you will not receive any financial or other incentives. Similarly, participating in this study will not incur any costs for you.

Confidentiality:

This research is based on ethical principles; therefore, the researchers guarantee the protection of the information collected and its strict use only for the present research. The results will be disseminated with the guarantee that no personal information can be identified, either within or outside the study.

Participant's Rights:

If you decide to participate in the questionnaire, however, at any time you feel uncomfortable or unsure about providing the required information, you have the right to withdraw at any time without fear of reprisals. Similarly, you have the right to choose not to participate, without any negative consequences. If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact the researcher.

CONSENT:

I freely and voluntarily agree to participate in this study. I am aware that unforeseen situations may arise during my participation. I have also been informed that I have the right to withdraw from participation at any time, even if I have previously agreed to participate. I will be provided with a copy of the informed consent form that I have signed.